

Ensuring safety of the commercial air transport industry under tight budget constraints

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Abstract. The article identifies the problems associated with ensuring the safe operation of air transport in the countries that have tight budget opportunities from the state's industry support. A number of factors that have a significant impact on the creation of an air safety system are outlined. Financial and non-financial measures for overcoming the obstacles to access the financial resources by national carriers and for directing the funds raised to improve the transport safety have been proposed.

In today's environment of increasing competition in high-tech industries, the problems related to the safety of air traffic and transportation come to the fore. This task is especially acute for the governments of the countries experiencing tight budget constraints on the development of the aviation industry. If highly developed countries with a large budget can choose several investment and support areas for the aviation industry and invest in improving their security, the countries with tight budget constraints have a shortage of funds to take such actions. Such states are characterized by an extremely low level of capital investments, the predominance of obsolete airplanes in the fleet, low return on invested capital, restrictions on the involvement of high-precision diagnostic devices, the absence of a targeted segment of accumulation of long-term financial resources in the financial market.

The high-tech industries, which largely determine the degree of development of countries and their technological structure, generally include air transport and commercial air transport in particular. The importance of the aviation industry in the system of industrial and economic relations of the country and the need for state stimulation of its development have been repeatedly emphasized by scientists Arefyeva O.V., Kulaev Y.F., Ovsak O.P., Yun G.M., including the authors of the publication Ivanytska O.M., Vysotska M.P. [1,2]. The issue of ensuring the safety of air transport and the role of the state in these processes are disclosed in the works of Kozlyuk I.O., Shtangret A.M. [3]. At the same time, solving the problem remains a challenge that requires new approaches and technologies.

Ukraine belongs to the countries with tight budget constraints. The country's import orientation, its focus on exports of low-capitalized product groups, the general production decline, the breakdown of economic ties with a number of customers of Ukrainian high-tech goods and political problems gave rise to severe restrictions in a number of industries, including aviation, which led to the decrease in the safety of its operation (fig.1, fig.2).

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Fig. 1 Expenditures of the state budget of Ukraine on air transport in 2015-2018 according to the functional classification of expenditures and crediting of the budget, mln UAH

Note: Made in accordance with the [Report of the State Treasury Service of Ukraine for 2015-2018. URL: <https://www.treasury.gov.ua/en>]

The data presented in Fig. 1 testify the following facts. First of all, the amount of money allocated for the budget support for the air fleet is extremely small. Starting from 60.4 mln UAH in 2014, it was actually spent on average 76.7 million UAH over the period of 2015-2016 and about 220 million UAH on average over the period of 2017-2018. Secondly, there is a systematic underperformance of the allocation plan by 3 and more percent.

Fig 2. Costs for overcoming the consequences of aviation incidents for 2015-2018, mln UAH.

Note: Made in accordance with the [Report of the State Treasury Service of Ukraine for 2015-2018. URL: <https://www.treasury.gov.ua/en>]

As it can be seen from the data in Fig. 2 the costs for overcoming the consequences of aviation incidents in average were from 6 million to 18 million UAH annually (\$ 230,000- \$ 700,000).

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In 2018 1,171,991,894 UAH was earmarked for the creation of a unified aviation security and civil defense system.

The situation is complicated by the fact that the aviation industry is the follower (not the innovator) of technology [4, p.6]. The aviation industry in any country “absorbs” the results of the scientific research of many areas of science and technology, in particular metallurgy, resistance of metals, aerodynamics etc. Consequently, the safety of transport depends on the total funding of scientific developments that are being implemented in the country. Despite the fact that Ukraine is able to implement the complete cycle of aircraft production, starting from design development and ending up with a serial production of the aircraft, the defining limiting factor of sustainable development of the country's fleet and its safety is a small amount of scientific research funding at all.

Another factor is the low ability of airlines to raise funds in the national financial market, which, as a rule, lacks both reliable instruments and a sufficient number of investors. At the same time, flight safety creates strict requirements for initial and supportive investments for the creation of market infrastructure: formation of a sufficient national support network of aerodromes, ensuring the quality of landing, carrying out scientific and technical explorations for improving the level of flight reliability and so on. The possibility of attracting and developing such investments is created under the conditions of prioritization of the industry in the vector of socio-economic development of the country. One of the tasks of attracting foreign investments in the aviation industry is to develop a program of its state guarantee as a priority.

Therefore, governments with limited budget resources are tasked with finding the best balance between budget financing for aviation security and creating the conditions for airlines to search for sources of funding, particularly in the capital market. The top priorities of the governments of the countries include stimulating the implementation and institutionalization of relations on the use of new instruments in the capital market focused specifically on financing the industry; facilitating the search of the reliable sources of financing by the companies and the formation of a system of providing state guarantees; the use of non-financial mechanisms to stimulate the development of the aviation industry by the state.

We have grouped the factors influencing the development of the national aviation industry and identified among them those which in our view require their primary consideration and the development of management decisions by state authorities.

The first group of factors includes those which are related to the regulation of air traffic security processes by the supranational authorities. First of all, it is about the ICAO (International Civil Aviation Organization) requirements for the development of a flight safety program by the government agencies. In addition to specialized requirements, the EU rules and standards also apply for the organization of flights. One of the areas that is being actively promoted by the EU countries is the creation of Common Aviation Area (CAA). At the same time, in order to join the CAA, national governments must adopt the rules of the game, navigation standards and amend national acts accordingly [5]. In particular, for Ukraine the signing of the SAP Agreement requires the incorporation of 64 EU regulations and directives, which takes not only time, political will, change of government mechanisms, but also financial regulation of tariffs, air and ground service prices, abolition of restrictions on competition in the provision of services inside the airports, etc. [6].

Adaptation of the aviation industry infrastructure to these requirements remains difficult for Ukraine and other countries with severe budget constraints. In particular, it is

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about the division of airports into categories, as required by the Council of Europe Directive [96.67.EU](#) and the bringing the level of regional airports to the proper standards of service and safety.

The group of factors affecting the distribution of spheres of influence in the commercial aviation market raises the question of the country's occupation of a particular market niche in the international air transport market. In fact, the airspace is already divided between powerful players, represented not only by regions (with North American as a dominating region) and countries but also by companies. In 2018 four companies - Airbus, Boeing, Lockheed Martin and Textron collected about 60% of the revenue generated by the industry in the international market [7]. The boom in the aviation market in recent years has shown that the revenue-generating industry is attractive to new entrants. Despite the fact that new players are actively entering aviation (especially from Latin American countries), the "old" players are not going to leave it: the commercial aviation market remains highly concentrated, both territorially and by certain companies. The same applies to the aviation leasing market.

There is the question of finding an optimal market niche that would take full advantage of the national aviation industry and its potential for the countries that intend to join the powerful air fleet community but have low levels of government financial support for the industry. We believe that international operating leasing will be able to meet the strategic objectives of building a national air transportation system, which has been repeatedly stated in scientific publications [8]. At the same time, it will be advisable to combine traditional leasing with innovative tools, which are used poorly or not used in Ukraine at all.

The well-known and widely used instrument of air transport leasing in foreign countries is tax-oriented lease or true lease. "Real" leasing is a form of long-term operating leasing, which involves the transfer of assets to the lessee on the basis of monthly payments made by the latter and the maximum preservation of the property in the condition in which it received it. The lessor retains the ability to obtain tax benefits, accelerate depreciation and the lessee declares the lease payments as capital expenditures. At the end of the term it is possible to redeem the leased asset. In the aviation industry this form of leasing relationship is beneficial for all parties involved. If the industry has tax benefits, the leasing aviation company retains the ability to receive them, and the lessee has more preferential terms for paying the lease payments. We believe that the terms of the contract may stipulate a condition for improvement by the lessee of the leased asset to ensure greater safety of flights, which will reduce the amount of payments.

Another promising form of rental (leasing) relationship is Graduated Lease under which the lessee and the lessor agree to a periodic adjustment of lease payments. This form will be especially useful when used in domestic, national leasing. Leasing payments can be linked to terms of airplanes use, currency fluctuations, inflation, changes in market conditions and etc.

Therefore, airlines need to establish close cooperative relationships with banking entities. We consider it is important for the group of countries with the budget constraints to set up a specialized bank to finance the industry, using the international experience of creating such financial institutions. It should be noted that the most developed approaches are in the USA, where there are powerful financial institutions which serve the aviation industry. Moreover, the conditions provided are quite attractive: the interest rate is about 4% and the loan term is from 15 to 20 years. Among the largest financial institutions are

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Aircraft Banking Centers (Orlando), Bank of Stockton (Stockton), Banterra Bank Aircraft Finance (Herrin) and others [9]. To estimate the scope of possible financial inflows, we provide the data from Aviation Finance Group (AFG). It was formed in 1998 as a private aircraft lender. AFG created the original asset-based corporate aircraft financing program. In 2004, PNC acquired AFG and formally changed the name to PNC Aviation Finance. In December 2008, PNC Financial Services Group, Inc. acquired National City Bank, which included National City Corporate Air. The PNC Aviation Finance company specializes exclusively on corporate aircraft financing with over \$ 3 billion in loans to the aviation industry over the past 5 years [10].

Therefore, in the context of limited budgetary resources the governments of the countries with high levels of scientific and technical potential, Ukraine in particular, must determine the financial and non-financial measures to promote capital raising in the aviation sector and to ensure the safety of transportation. This involves identifying the factors that mostly influence the status and sources of funding for the industry as well as developing policies to counteract their negative impact.

The following areas of state decision making include: the need to incorporate the rules, regulations, standards regarding the security of the provision of aviation and related services into the national legislation; prioritizing the development of aviation ground infrastructure for attracting investors, including foreign ones; substantiation of measures for search of more or less “free” market niches in the international aviation business and concentration of efforts on their occupation; institutionalizing the use of the latest financial instruments to attract financial revenues, in particular through national and international leasing; facilitating the establishment of banking institutions focused solely or predominantly on the service of the aviation industry; creating a state fund that would facilitate the participation of medium-sized and small aviation companies in stock market operations and hedge financial risks; defining state guarantee mechanisms for national airlines loans.

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